

File Format Guidance for Researchers

The table below provides general guidelines for researchers outlining the differences between proprietary and open formats. In general, open formats are encouraged as the probability of continued access and reuse is higher. However, not all research can use open formats.

Open	Proprietary formats	Proprietary, but open
No restrictions on use. Format specification freely available	Owned and controlled by a company	Proprietary, but the specification may be published (in whole or part)
Can be correctly read by a range of different software programs. Fully functional in at least one free software	Typically requires proprietary software to read files reliably	Freeware options to visualize or analyze files, but may not have full functionality
Often an open standard, maintained by non-commercial expert body	Format description confidential, and subject to change at any time	Format description subject to change at any time, controlled by company
.csv, .txt, .mzml, .cif, .hdf5, .dcm, .fasta, .tiff, .jpg	.qgd, .fid, .dld, .spm, .wiff, accdb, .xls	.mat, .nb, .xlsx, .shp